

SIMULATED TESTS OF LARGE SAMPLES INDICATE A LOGARITHMIC EXTREME VALUE DISTRIBUTION IN ELECTROMIGRATION INDUCED FAILURES OF THIN-FILM INTERCONNECTS

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Abstract

In electromigration failure studies it is generally assumed that electromigration induced failures may be adequately modelled by a log normal distribution. Several research works have proved the inefficiency of this modelling and have indicated the possible applicability of the logarithmic distribution of extreme values. This is especially important in the case of early failures distribution. To further examine this possibility a novel electromigration model was created, using an object oriented and fully 2-dimensional electrical and thermal sub-models. The repeated simulations performed show that the log extreme value distribution is a better statistical model for electromigration failures. The significance of such a modelling is particularly apparent in electromigration failure rate prediction.

1. Introduction

Electromigration in metal conductors has been originally observed by H.B. Huntington in 1961¹. Nevertheless, most of the quantitative understanding of this complex failure mechanism is still based on empirical formulae and assumptions. One such assumption, widely adopted in the related literature, is that electromigration median failure times obey a log normal distribution². It was also suggested that such a distribution is in fact indicative of electromigration induced failures³. However one of the known disadvantages of the log normal distribution is that, over a reasonable range of parameters, data following other distributions will appear linear on a log normal cumulative failure plot⁴. As a result of this alternative distributions have been suggested, namely the Weibull distribution and the logarithmic extreme value distribution (LEV)^{13,14,15,16}. The selection of the appropriate statistics is critical for the accurate prediction of conductor reliability, but the small samples commonly tested do not allow a clear distinction to be made. Isolated attempts to test large numbers of samples have concentrated on the bimodal characteristics of the distribution¹². One of the methods circumventing this problem is the use of simulation techniques. The simulation models presented in the past deal with the determination of the most appropriate distribution^{6,7,8,9}. It has been noted that aluminium life test data fit the log normal and the Weibull distribution equally well at relatively large failure percentages, but at the most interesting lower failure percentages show substantial discrepancies⁸. On the other

hand simulated data give a clear indication that the LEV distribution gives a tighter fit compared to both log normal and Weibull, under a wide range of parameters. In particular it was argued that LEV distribution gives equally good results when used with grain sizes exceeding the conductor's line width and with grain sizes smaller than the line width, whereas the log normal distribution models accurately only the latter case⁷. These conclusions were later contradicted, using smallest extreme value statistics^{4,11}. Nevertheless it should be noted that the logarithmic smallest extreme values distribution, or Type II, corresponds to a simplified Weibull distribution, quite remote from the log largest extreme values originally used¹⁴.

The assumption that LEV distribution is a better alternative to the ones already widely used may also be theoretically justified. Given that the grain size is log normally distributed, the time to failure of each section of the conductor should also be log normally distributed. Since the time to failure of the entire conductor is the time to failure of a number of parallel weakest sections, statistics predict that the time to failure of the conductor should follow a LEV distribution^{5,10}. The fact that Weibull grain size distributions are adequately fitted by a log normal distribution⁶ is explained by the simple fact that in any case Weibull data fit a log normal distribution reasonably well⁷.

The work presented here attempts to most suitably fit data obtained from simulated tests performed on AlCu interconnects, under four different test conditions compared to one AlCu data set tested with our in-house facilities. Data were in turn fitted to a log normal, a Weibull and a LEV distribution. Tightness of fit was examined by probability plots, using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the correlation coefficient (r).

2. Simulation results and statistical analysis

Earlier works have indicated the advantages of object-oriented programming for VLSI simulation and design¹⁷. The software for the electromigration simulation was developed in a Smalltalk V for Windows environment and each grain in the VLSI conductor was as a separate object subclass with a set of physical properties and interrelations with neighbouring grains. The simulation software firstly generates a Voronoi diagram, based on a selected statistical distribution, and then the interconnect size is selected visually (Fig 1).

The actual model uses a 2-dimensional thermal model to calculate temperatures and a 2-dimensional electrical model to calculate the current density J_x . The atomic flux is calculated by Huntington's formula across the grain boundaries :

$$J_x = (ND/kT)Z^*eE = (ND/kT)Z^*e\rho j$$

The electrical model constantly monitors resistance and voltage and the sample is considered to have failed when there is a resistance increase over $dR/R=20\%$ or when an open circuit is detected. The simulation experiments concerned 4 batches of 100 Al/Cu(4%) interconnects with grain size exceeding the linewidth in temperatures ranging from 183°C-235°C. The stress current density was 4×10^6 A/cm².

Figure 1. A selected Al/Cu interconnect

Life data were in turn fitted to the three distribution mostly applied for electromigration life data. It was apparent that the Weibull distribution is an inadequate model in all cases, whereas the comparison between the other two distributions was more difficult. Therefore we have employed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to quantify the goodness of fit. The critical values obtained were quite high and we have used them as figures of merit for each distribution. The results are shown in table 1. A least squares test has confirmed these results as well.

As a comparative measure, we have tested a batch of real Al/Cu interconnects in our test facility, comprising of an oven, DC current sources and an HP measurement and control system. The 3.0 μ m line width was exceeding the film grain size in this case as well. The first 2 samples failed after 2 hours, quickly followed by another 3 samples. The last sample failed after 155 hours of stressing (Photo 1). The early failures were expected due to the high test temperature and stress current (230°C, 4x10⁶A/cm²).

DATA SET	LOG NORMAL	LEV	WEIBULL
Al/Cu 180° +	0.097	0.038	0.135
Al/Cu 200° +	0.089	0.043	0.178
Al/Cu 220° +	0.076	0.045	0.136
Al/Cu 235° +	0.105	0.056	0.176
Al/Cu 230° *	0.194	0.183	0.210

* Real Test, +Simulated Tests

Table 1. Max |xi-Ei| values (Ei=expected rank, xi=rank)

A graphical representation of the results for the log extreme value and the lognormal

distribution is shown in figures 3 and 4 respectively. Figure 2 shows the statistical analysis results from an early software developed within the group, where the correlation coefficients for the three distributions are apparent.

Photo 1: Characteristic open-circuit failure due to electromigration. The triangular void is due to the thermal stress that preceded the electromigration tests.

3. Conclusion

It has been shown that life data from four simulated and one real electromigration test on AlCu mono-layer thin film interconnects are tighter fitted to a log extreme value distribution compared to a Weibull or a Log normal one. In all cases line width exceeded the median grain size of the films. This has a particular significance when it comes to predicting the reliability of thin-film interconnects, which is depending on the distribution applied.

REFERENCES

1. H.B.Huntington and A.R.Grone, "Current-induced marker motion in gold wires", *J.Phys.Chem.Solids*, vol.20, nos 1/2, p.76, 1961
2. H.Schafft, J.A.Lechner, B.Sabi, M.Mahaney and R.C.Smith, "Statistics for electromigration testing", in *Proc.26th IEEE Int. Reliability Physics Symp.*, p.192, 1988
3. Laura Brooke, "Pulsed Current Electromigration Failure Model", in *Proc. 25th IEEE Int. Reliability Physics Symp.*, p.136, 1987
4. D.J.LaCombe and E.L.Parks, "The distribution of electromigration failures", in *Proc.24th IEEE Int.Reliability Physics Symp.*, p.1, 1986
5. J.R.King, "*Probability charts for decision making*", Industrial Press, New York, 1971, Chap.23

6. M.J.Attardo, R.Rutledge and R.C.Jack, "Statistical metallurgical model for electromigration failure in aluminum thin-film conductors", *J.Appl.Phys.*, vol.42, no.11, p.4343, 1971
7. J.M.Schoen, "Monte Carlo calculations of structure-induced electromigration failure", *J.Appl.Phys.*, vol.51, no.1, p.513, 1980
8. K.Nikawa, "Monte Carlo calculations based on the generalized electromigration failure model", in *Proc.19th IEEE Int.Reliability Physics Symp.*, p.175, 1981
9. P.J.Marcoux, P.P.Merchant, V.Naroditsky and W.D.Rehder, "A new 2D simulation model of electromigration", *Hewlett-Packard J.*, vol.40, no.3, p.79, 1989
10. P.D.T.O'Connor, "*Practical reliability engineering*", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, 1986, p.40
11. Janet M.Towner, "Are electromigration failures lognormally distributed?", in *Proc. 28th IEEE Int. Reliability Physics Symp.*, p.100, 1990
12. H.H.Hoang, E.L.Nikkel, J.M.McDavid and R.B.MacNaughton, "Electromigration early-failure distribution", *J.Appl.Phys.*, vol.65, no.3, p.1044, 1989
13. M.I.Loupis, J.N.Avaritsiotis, "Probability distribution modelling of electromigration induced failure times", in *Proc. MELECON '91*, vol. 1, pp.259-262, 1991
14. M.I.Loupis, J.N.Avaritsiotis, "Experimental Set-Up for Electromigration Tests - First Results", *Esprit BASE-TIP project, Report: NTUA/ESPRIT 2016/020/20.01.92*, January 1992
15. M.I. Lcupis, J.N.Avaritsiotis, "The applicability of logarithmic extreme value distributions in electromigration induced failures of Al/Cu thin-film interconnects", *Microelectronics and Reliability Journal*, no.11, 1994.
16. M.I. Lcupis, J.N.Avaritsiotis,G.D.Tziallas, "Comparative study of statistical distributions in electromigration induced failures of Al/Cu thin-film interconnects", *Active and Passive Electronic Components*, vol.16, no. 2, 1994, pp.119-126
17. M.I. Loupis, G.D.Tziallas, "A knowledge-based framework for VLSI design", *Micro processing and Microprogramming*, vol.28, nos 1-5, March 1990, pp.327-332.

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 Statistical Analysis of Electromigration Life Data - version 2.0

Figure 2. Statistical analysis for test batch #4 at 235°C

LOG EXTREME VALUE FIT EXPERIMENT AT 235 C

Figure 3. Log Extreme Value fit for simulation batch #4

LOGNORMAL FIT EXPERIMENT AT 235 C

Figure 4. Log Normal fit for simulation batch #4